

DATA NOTE

Evaluating researcher and stakeholder perspectives on socially responsible research and innovation practices in research performing organisations [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Eric A. Jensen

Policy Research Unit, International Consortium of Research Staff Associations, Cork, Ireland

V1 First published: 14 Dec 2021, 1:150
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14325.1>

Latest published: 20 Jul 2023, 1:150
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14325.2>

Abstract

The European Commission-funded GRRIP (Grounding RRI Practices) project aims to embed sustainable Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices in five research performing organisations (RPOs), focusing on the marine and maritime sector. The project's goal is to achieve institutional and cultural change through a cycle of evaluation, evidence-based interventions and further evaluation. For this purpose, a set of three surveys were designed and implemented in the first part of the project (2020) to establish a baseline measurement of RRI-related practices within the project partner institutions and their stakeholders. Each survey was specifically designed to target a relevant category of people for each of the five RPOs implementing RRI actions. These five institutions are research departments and centres linked to the marine and maritime sector in Ireland, Spain, Portugal, France and the UK. This paper presents the design of these survey-based evaluation instruments and the linked datasets generated by their implementation.

Keywords

RRI, socially responsible science, researchers, scientists, indicators, evaluation

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 20 Jul 2023	 view	
version 1 14 Dec 2021	 view	

1. **Ross S. Bailie**, University of Sydney, Lismore, Australia

2. **Mercedes Ruiz-Lozano** , Universidad Loyola Andalucía, Sevilla, Spain

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

This article is included in the [Research on Research gateway](#).

Corresponding author: Eric A. Jensen (eric.jensen@sruc.ac.uk)

Author roles: **Jensen EA:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Lorenz L:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This research was financially supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 820283 (project GRRIP).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2021 Jensen EA and Lorenz L. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Jensen EA and Lorenz L. **Evaluating researcher and stakeholder perspectives on socially responsible research and innovation practices in research performing organisations [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2021, 1:150 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14325.1>

First published: 14 Dec 2021, 1:150 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14325.1>

Plain language summary

There has been a longstanding movement in the global research community to make research and innovation more useful to society. These efforts have been linked to a wide range of approaches to make research practices more socially responsible, that is, more inclusive, transparent and publicly accessible. This paper focuses on a particular aspect of such initiatives, namely, how to measure progress towards more socially responsible research practices and policies at the level of research institutions. Here, specific approaches to doing this with survey methods are described, alongside the data from a pilot effort to implement these surveys in five research organisations across Europe.

Introduction

The European Commission-funded **GRRIP** (Grounding RRI Practices) project aims to embed sustainable Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices in five research performing organisations (RPOs), focusing on the marine and maritime sector. The project's goal is to achieve institutional and cultural change through a cycle of evaluation, evidence-based interventions and further evaluation. For this purpose, a set of three surveys were designed and implemented in the first part of the project to evaluate current RRI practices within the project partner institutions and their stakeholders. Each survey was specifically designed to target a relevant category of people for each of the five RPOs implementing RRI actions. These five institutions are research departments and centres linked to the marine and maritime sector in Ireland, Spain, Portugal, France and the UK:

- The Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy (MaREI), University College Cork, Ireland
- Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (Plocan), Gran Canaria
- WavEC Offshore Renewables, Lisbon, Portugal
- Institut Universitaire Mer Littoral U.Nantes (IUML), France
- Swansea University, Wales

Materials and methods

Research instruments

RPO survey. The RPO survey was designed to evaluate the presence and availability of RRI-related policy and guidance within each of the five marine and maritime research organisations. Respondents were asked to indicate whether policy or guidance covering a specific RRI dimension was available within their institution and also provide the full documents or text passages of relevant policies accordingly. The RRI-related topics covered in this survey were:

- Gender Equality
- Open Access Publications
- Public Engagement
- Research Ethics and Integrity
- Science Education and Outreach

In addition to the documentation of reported RRI-related policies and guidance, the survey also asked whether the respondent's organisation had any dedicated staff, meetings, training or other organisational structures in place to monitor and enable RRI practices.

Researcher and stakeholder surveys. Both designed to deliver RRI indicators (Jensen & Lister, 2015) for impact evaluation purposes (e.g., Jensen, 2015; Jensen, 2020), the researcher and stakeholder surveys (described below) were aligned to work in tandem and are therefore similar in several ways. However, the researcher survey was targeted towards people who work in research performing organisations in the marine and maritime sector, while the stakeholder survey was aimed at those who have links or collaborations with the five RPOs in the project to find out whether RRI was being implemented in a way that was recognised by stakeholders.

The content of the two surveys focused on the policies and practices employed by each of the five marine and maritime organisations involved in the project. Respondents were first asked to provide some personal information about themselves and their career, such as employment status, experience, and scientific field of work. Furthermore, they were asked about how they incorporate RRI practices in their own work and how much time they dedicate to engage in both research and research-related work (e.g., communication, management or administration). The survey then proceeded to gather information about respondents' views on the RPOs' implementation of a range of different RRI dimensions, such as workforce diversity, gender equality, inclusion of ethnic minorities, alignment with societal needs and ethics.

Research instrument design

Sampling. Respondents were recruited differently for each survey. The RPO survey was completed by designated representatives of the five marine and maritime RPOs in the project implementing RRI actions. The researcher survey was completed by people who worked at these same RPOs, while the stakeholder survey was sent to people linked to the RPOs but working in a range of sectors. These participants were recruited by the project representatives at each of these sites through department or institution wide requests for participation. Specific information about the type of researchers or stakeholders responding were captured within the survey to be considered in the analysis. Survey data were collected March - June 2020.

The dataset collected using the instruments described above was cleansed according to established social research good practice (e.g., Jensen & Laurie, 2016; Smith & Jensen, 2016). As a first step, all data was completely anonymised where personally identifiable information was provided by respondents. Further, all insufficiently completed responses were removed, such as respondents who discontinued the survey after a few questions. It is available in both SPSS and CSV formats to maximise compatibility across different devices and research tools (Lorenz & Jensen, 2021a; Lorenz & Jensen, 2021b; Lorenz & Jensen, 2021c).

Dataset validation

The survey data collection operated with a focus on evaluation. Therefore, the goal was to gain a broad base of participation, as much as was feasible during the available timeframe. The datasets themselves cannot be taken as fully representative samples of their institutions, and certainly not of European research institutions more generally. Rather, these data offer an initial exploration of the status of these particular institutions on a number of different metrics at the outset of a culture change process aimed at bolstering the level of breadth of socially responsible research and innovation policies and practices at these locations.

Data availability

Zenodo: GRRIP WP5 - RPO Survey. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708901> (Lorenz & Jensen, 2021a).

This project contains the following underlying data:

- GRRIP_RPO_survey_data_documentation.pdf

Zenodo: GRRIP WP5 - Researcher Survey. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708878> (Lorenz & Jensen, 2021b).

This project contains the following underlying data:

- GRRIP_researcher_survey_data_CSV.csv
- GRRIP_researcher_survey_data_documentation.pdf
- GRRIP_researcher_survey_data_SPSS.sav
- GRRIP_researcher_survey_structure.csv

Zenodo: GRRIP WP5 - Stakeholder Survey. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708883> (Lorenz & Jensen, 2021c).

This project contains the following underlying data:

- GRRIP_stakeholder_survey_data_CSV.csv
- GRRIP_stakeholder_survey_data_documentation.pdf
- GRRIP_stakeholder_survey_data_SPSS.sav
- GRRIP_stakeholder_survey_structure.csv

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](#) (CC-BY 4.0).

GRRIP WP5 - RPO Survey full datasets have not been made publicly available because the project deemed the datasets generated from this survey to be confidential.

Ethics policies and consent

The data were collected under the auspices of ethics approval by the relevant University College Cork institutional review board, the Social Research Ethics Committee (application date: 14 August 2019) for the GRRIP project. Written informed consent for publication of the participants' details and/or their images was obtained from the participants in all cases, in line with the General Data Protection Regulation.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank all the partners in the GRRIP project consortium for their support, as well as Dr Gordon Dalton as project coordinator. We would like to register special thanks for the participants and those who organised data collection at the Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy (MaREI), University College Cork, Ireland; Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (Plocan), Gran Canaria; WavEC Offshore Renewables, Lisbon, Portugal Institut Universitaire Mer Littoral U.Nantes (IUML), France and Swansea University, Wales.

References

Jensen E: **Highlighting the value of impact evaluation: Enhancing informal science learning and public engagement theory and practice.** *JCOM J Sci Commun.* 2015; **14**(3): Y05. [Publisher Full Text](#)

Jensen EA: **How should socially responsible science be measured? (eLetter).** *Science.* 2020; **369**(6499). [Publisher Full Text](#)

Jensen E, Laurie C: **Doing real research: A practical guide to social research.** SAGE: London, 2016. [Reference Source](#)

Jensen EA, Lister TP: **Evaluating indicator-based methods of 'measuring long-term impacts of a science center on its community'.** *J Res Sci Teach.*

2015; **53**(1): 60-64.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Lorenz L, Jensen E: **GRRIP WP5 - RPO Survey (1.0) [Data set].** *Zenodo.* 2021a. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708901>

Lorenz L, Jensen E: **GRRIP WP5 - Researcher Survey (1.0) [Data set].** *Zenodo.* 2021b. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708878>

Lorenz L, Jensen E: **GRRIP WP5 - Stakeholder Survey (1.0) [Data set].** *Zenodo.* 2021c. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708883>

Smith BK, Jensen EA: **Critical review of the United Kingdom's "gold standard" survey of public attitudes to science.** *Public Underst Sci.* 2016; **25**(2): 154-170. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 06 April 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15456.r28813>

© 2022 Ruiz-Lozano M. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Mercedes Ruiz-Lozano

Department of Financial Economics and Accounting, Universidad Loyola Andalucía, Sevilla, Spain

This data note presents research that is very appropriate since the research centers must respond to the needs of society and also create value for it, but this can only be achieved by disseminating the results so that all stakeholders, involved or affected, can make decisions. Likewise, the centers that finance their research with public funds must be an example in the implementation of inclusion policies and ethical actions. There are some aspects that could be improved:

- The title of the research must mention the type of organizations analyzed.
- The objective is identified, but the reason for that objective is not clearly described. It is not described how the variables that are analyzed can respond to these objectives. With the surveys, guidelines for action will be identified. What will be the next steps?
- Organizations are clearly identified, but why these organizations have been chosen is not made clear. Is homogeneity sought in order to identify best practices or is diversity sought to identify possible patterns of action? It is not identified if the sample is representative and homogeneous by country.
- Science Education and Outreach. This topic is not clearly identified in the survey. What is it referring to? How has it been analyzed?
- The researchers indicate that the survey also asked whether the respondent's organisation had any dedicated staff, meetings, training or other organisational structures in place to monitor and enable RRI practices. But these issues are not easily identified in the survey.
- The data is provided, but is not in a usable format because the data is accumulated in a single column. They should appear separated by rows and columns.

Thanks for sharing the research.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Partly

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Social responsibility, transparency, ethical codes

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 05 May 2023

Eric Jensen

Thanks very much for your helpful and constructive feedback! I have submitted an updated version of this article. Further details about this data have also been added to the Open Access Repository: <https://zenodo.org/record/6914524>.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 13 January 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15456.r28278>

© 2022 **Bailie R.** This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Ross S. Bailie

University Centre for Rural Health, University of Sydney, Lismore, NSW, Australia

This data note introduces a survey of five 'research performing organisations' that are involved in a project to embed sustainable responsible research and innovation practices. The paper is generally well-written. There are few points that should be addressed before the data note can be approved:

1. The links to the Researcher Survey and the Stakeholder Survey data show documents that appear to be identical with both being labelled 'Researcher Survey'. This needs to be

corrected.

2. In the Materials and Methods section the subheadings should be refined/corrected - the text under the subheading 'Research Instrument Design' refers to sampling of respondents and collection of the data, while info on the instrument design appears under the previous subheading. This could be fixed by removing the two level 1 subheadings and including a new subheading on 'Data Collection'.
3. The data Note could be improved by including information on inclusion/exclusion criteria for the sampling process.
4. The note could also be improved by clarification of the reference to 'department or institution wide requests for information' (in the paragraph labelled 'Sampling').
5. The Plain Language Summary refers to 'a pilot effort to implement these surveys', but there is no reference to this being a pilot in other sections of the note. It should be made clear if this was or was not a pilot study, and if so what were the aims and objectives of the pilot study.
6. It would be useful to include some commentary on lessons learned from this initial 'baseline' survey, what refinements have been or should be made to the survey methods and tools, and the extent to which the survey design and survey implementation are considered fit-for-purpose.
7. I suggest the title of the Data Note should be refined to more closely reflect the aim/purpose of the Data Note.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Health services and systems research

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 05 May 2023

Eric Jensen

Thanks very much for your helpful and constructive feedback! I have submitted an updated version of this article. Further details about this data have also been added to the Open Access Repository: <https://zenodo.org/record/6914524>.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
